

DESIGN, PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF BIOLOGICAL AUXETIC HYDROGELS WITH SHELL-CORE STRUCTURE

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Abstract The biological auxetic hydrogels can be used in the wide field of biomedical materials. However, there are few researches about preparation and properties of this kind of materials. According to the structures of auxetic molecular materials and composite materials which have already exhibited the negative Poisson's ratio effect, a kind of novel hydrogels with shell-core structure were designed and prepared. The deformation of the hydrogels under compressing was tested by the Digital Speckle Correlation Method (DSCM), and their displacements and Poisson's ratios were characterized. For the compressed hydrogels with shell-core structure, because of the asynchronous deformation between core and shell part, the middle area of the sample appeared concave shrink. The core's diameter had important influence on the deformation and Poisson's ratio of the samples.

1 Introduction

Auxetic materials, with special microstructure and mechanical properties of strange, are different from traditional materials. It expands horizontally when stretched in the elastic range but shrinks under compression. Since Lakes[1] has found for the first time in 1987 that two-dimensional honeycomb-like solid materials with the internal concave structural units have the negative Poisson's ratio effect, a variety of auxetic polymers, with different microstructure and deformation mechanism have been found and prepared, mainly including the auxetic porous polymers[2-4], auxetic composite materials[5-7] and auxetic molecular materials[8-10]. The design and preparation technology of such materials have achieved great breakthrough. The hydrogel, a kind of substance with a state between solid and liquid, is widespread in organisms. With the

negative Poisson's ratio effect, the auxetic hydrogel can effectively resist the shear force, and improve the elastic modulus, notch impact strength and fracture toughness. With the increase of negative Poisson's ratio, the shear modulus, storage modulus and static modulus of the auxetic hydrogel increase. As bionic implants for repaired soft tissues [11-13], such as blood vessel, nerve, cartilage, intervertebral discs and muscle ligament, the hydrogel can match better with the biological tissues and achieve physiological functions.

The physical cross-linking polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) hydrogel can be formed by the phase separation and crystallization of macromolecules during the process of repeated freezing-defrosting [14, 15]. In the international arena, the PVA hydrogels have been successfully used for artificial skin, dressing for burn or trauma, plastic infill, artificial vitreous, cornea, artificial blood vessel and artificial cartilage implant [16, 17]. The PVA hydrogels, formed through the typical chemical cross-linking or physical cross-linking, do not appear auxetic behaviors, and all the theoretic models to describe auxetic materials do not fit to hydrogels because of its super elastic. The researches on the preparation, characterization and deformation mechanism of the PVA hydrogels, with the negative Poisson's ratio effect and biological function, would provide important scientific foundations for the development of new biomaterials with high performances. However, there are few reports on the microstructure, morphology, deformation mechanism and macro-mechanical properties of the auxetic hydrogels and their applications of biological organization are lacking, either.

Through the analysis of the micro-structure model of existing auxetic molecular materials, we could find

out that the design principle of them was mainly that through the change of the number of acetylene connection at the vertical and diagonal of the benzene, the negative Poisson's ratio was achieved in theory. With the vertical compression, the single acetylene, on the diagonal line of benzene ring, depresses inward together with benzene ring. It leads to the mutually close of the rigid connection between each link segments, and the landscape orientation presents the state of contraction. According to the analysis, the PVA hydrogels with shell-core structure had been designed and prepared in this paper. The deformation of the hydrogels under compressing was tested by the Digital Speckle Correlation Method (DSCM), and their displacements and Poisson's ratios were characterized.

2 Materials and Methods

The PVA powders (type 17-99, polymerization degree 1750 ± 50 , average molecular weight 74800-79200 and alcoholysis degree 99.9%) were weighed quantitatively, and added into deionized water with a 30 wt% weight concentration of PVA. PVA hydrosol was prepared in an electro-thermic pressure steam sterilizer, with pressure of 0.24Mpa, temperature of 120°C, and time of 1.5 hours. After that, the mixture was injected into a stainless steel mold, and they all were put into a refrigerating installation with temperature of -20°C for 10 hours. The cores, 30 wt % PVA hydrogel, were prepared with its diameter of 12, 15 and 18 mm respectively. After freezing-defrosting, the core was cut into a cylinder with height of 25 mm. The core was fixed in the center section of a stainless steel cylindrical mold (inside diameter of 30.00 mm).

The polyoxyethylene alkyl phenyl ether (OP, TX-10) and the NaCl particles (150-200 mesh) were mixed in the 1:1 mass ratio as the composite pore-forming agent. In 5:1 mass ratio of PVA and the composite pore-forming agent, it was added into 15wt% PVA hydrosol. And then the 15 wt% PVA hydrosol, containing the composite pore-forming agent, was injected into the mold above. All they were put into a refrigerating installation with temperature of -20°C for 10 hours. After that, they defrosted in room temperature for 3 hours. Repeat the above steps six times, fashioned samples would be obtained. In order to get the samples of PVA hydrogel with shell-core structure, they were cleaned to remove the composite pore-forming agent, using an ultrasonic cleaner at 25°C for 1 hour.

The samples above were cut into cube shape (5×5×5mm), and put into a vacuum freeze dryer for freeze-drying till balance weight, then coated with gold in different directions. Their surface morphology was observed using a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM, Zeiss SUPRATM55).

In order to form artificial speckle pattern, amount of the black and white paint were sprayed alternately onto the sample surfaces which were to be tested. And then the samples were set on the loading platform of a mechanical testing machine for compression test. The loading speed for all samples was 2mm/min. Cold light source irradiates the sample surfaces, as shown in Fig. 2a. During the deformation process of the samples under loading, the surface speckle patterns of the samples were recorded using a charge-coupled device (CCD) camera.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Morphology of the hydrogels with shell-core structure

Fig. 1 shows the morphology of the hydrogel and interfaces between the shell and core. It is clearly seen that a shell-core structure was produced with the porous shell connected closely with the compact core. The distinct interface appeared of a sharp porosity gradient in a form of a fused layer with many topological interlocks between the shell and core. Such an interlocking interface is envisaged to form during the process. At the early stage of the sample preparation, the periphery of the hydrogel core could start swelling and dissolving once it was surrounded by warmer PVA hydrosol injected in the mold. The swollen and dissolved PVA chains from the core surface would gradually diffuse into the hydrosol and join in the gel formation during the freezing-thawing cycles resulting in the formation of the fused interlocking bonding at the interface.

3.2 Analysis of the deformation of the hydrogels

Fig. 2 showed the macro-deformation of the PVA hydrogels with shell-core (18 mm) structure under axial compression. In the process of compression, a single structure appears the concave phenomenon. With the increase of the load, the deformations at the top and bottom of the sample were larger, and the deformation of the middle was smaller as the presence of the core. Due to the non-synchronized deformation, the middle of the sample was not only under the vertical pressure, but also extruded inward

pressure from the top and bottom of the sample. As shown with the arrows in Fig. 2c, the middle of the sample showed the state of lateral contraction. So the integral structure after repeated arrangement of the single structure would achieve contraction of the landscape orientation.

The PVA hydrogels are elastic and have larger deformation ever the force smaller, so they are not suitable for means of strain gauges. During the analysis of specimen deformation under load, we adopted a new testing method that DSCM. It is a kind of non-contact panoramic testing technology based on the speckle correlations of sample surface before and after the deformation to determine their displacements. In this method, the speckles, recorded in the surface digital images of the samples under loading, were analyzed using mathematical correlation method, namely their deformation (displacement) was accurately determined by the gray value model of the digital images [18, 19].

Obviously, the transverse displacements varied across different parts of the samples attributed to the shell-core structure with a combination of different elastic modulus. We calculated and analyzed the three zones of the digital speckle pattern, as shown in Fig. 3a. Fig. 3b clearly quantifies the non-uniform transverse deformation across the different zones. The lines of equal displacement in zone 1 and 3 were dense, with the transverse displacement about 1.4 and 1.2 respectively. While in zone 2, the displacement became smaller, only about 0.7. Similar results were achieved through the quantitative measurements of displacements of the other samples with different core diameters, in agreement with the macroscopic biconcave-shape deformation.

Through calculating the displacement in the different parts of the samples, the influence of the cores' diameter to the sample deformation could be determined. Fig. 4a showed the load-displacement curves of the PVA hydrogels with different diameter of the core. The deformation curves of the hydrogels with shell-core structure were similar to that of the porous hydrogels. Fig. 4b showed the Poisson's ratio-displacement curves of the PVA hydrogels with different diameter of the core. With the increasing of the displacement of the hydrogels, their Poisson's ratio gradually decreased, and the larger the core's diameter, their Poisson's ratio smaller. The Poisson's ratio of the samples with the core diameter of 18mm is 0.38, smaller than the rest two groups of samples (the core diameter, 12 and 15 mm), which is 0.45. Such results were consistent with compression deformation results of the samples with different

core's diameter. It demonstrated that the core's diameter had important influence on the deformation and Poisson's ratio of the samples.

4 Conclusions

Shell-core PVA hydrogels with a sharp porosity gradient were design and fabricated. Strong topological interlock bonding at the interface of the shell-core structure was formed during the freezing-thawing process. Unique biconcave-shape deformation occurred under axial compression with a lateral contraction in the middle zone of the samples. The core diameter had an important influence on the deformation and Poisson's ratio of the samples. The larger the core diameter, the smaller their Poisson's ratio is.

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Fig.1. Morphology of the interface region of the PVA hydrogels with shell-core (core diameter, 18 mm) structure.

Fig. 2. The macro-deformation of the PVA hydrogels with shell-core (18 mm) structure under axial compression.

Fig.3. The analysis area (a) of the digital speckle pattern and corresponding lines of equal displacement (b) in the lateral displacement field of the PVA hydrogels with shell-core (18 mm) structure.

Fig.4. The load-displacement (a) and Poisson's ratio - displacement (b) curves of the PVA hydrogels with different diameter of the core.

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